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Bonus Share Issue by Indian Companies – A Study of Automobile Companies

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The main objective of this paper is to examine the overall trend of bonus issues by Indian Automobile Industry since liberalization. The paper also focuses over the size of the company and the bonus issue ratio used by them. The study covers bonus issues made during 1991-2009 by the Indian automobile companies (public and private) listed on stock exchange. The sample of listed Indian automobile companies have been selected on various basis such as size of the company, frequency of bonus issues, ratio of bonus issues and time lag between two bonus issues. The period selected for this paper is marked by major changes in the earlier guidelines for the bonus issues by the CCI (Ministry of Finance). Thereafter, SEBI was introduced in the year 1992 to regulate and control the securities market in India with a view to investor's protection. For the first time, SEBI has issued a guideline for Bonus Share Issues for Disclosure and Investor's Protection on June 11, 1992. This guideline was modified on 13th and 15th April, 1994 respectively. There is also a drastic change in Government Policies, Corporate Dividend Policy, Companies Performance etc.

Bonus Share Issues by Automobile Companies - Recent Trends

Out of the total 50 automobile companies, only 4 companies belonged to the private sector and the rest of the companies were from public sector. Majority of the bonus issues were from the large scale companies. Companies like Banco Products, Motherson Sumi Systems Ltd., Punjab Tractors Ltd. etc. have made a bonus issue for more than two times during the nineteen year period. Some companies like Hero Honda Ltd, Hi-Tech Gears Ltd, Mahindra & Mahindra Ltd., etc. have made a bonus issue for two times. It is also noticed that no private company have repeated bonus issue during the period under study.

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Table 1**Analysis of Bonus Ratios of Automobile Companies**

Company	Ratio	Year
Amzel Auto	1:2	1991
Punj Tractors	1:1	1992
Schrader Duncan	1:1	1993
Rane Engines	1:1	1994
Hero Honda	1:4	1994
United Motors	1:1	1995
Banco Products	1:2	1995
UCAL Fuel	1:5	1995
Mah and Mah	2:3	1995
Tata Motors	3:5	1995
Sundram-Clayto	1:1	1996
Punj Tractors	1:1	1996
Rane Engine	1:1	1996
Schrader Duncan	1:1	1996
PAE	1:2	1996
Federal-Mogul	1:2	1996
Mah Scooters	1:1	1997
Motherson Sumi	1:2	1997
Munjaj Showa	1:1	1998
Hero Honda	1:1	1998
Banco Products	1:1	1999
VST Tillers	1:2	1999
Hi-Tech Gears	1:1	2000
Motherson Sumi	1:2	2000
Punj Tractors	2:1	2000
Amtek Auto	1:1	2002
Machino Plastic	1:1	2002
Rico Auto	1:1	2002
Omax Autos	5:1	2002
India Nippon	7:10	2002
Exide Industrie	1:1	2003
UCAL Fuel	1:1	2004
Subros	1:1	2004
Suprajit Eng	1:1	2004
Rane Brake	1:1	2004
Pricol	1:2	2004
Talbro Auto	5:2	2004

Cont.....

Mah and Mah	1:1	2005
ZF Steering Gea	1:1	2005
Hi-Tech Gears	1:1	2005
Motherson Sumi	1:2	2005
Jay Bharat Marut	1:1	2006
Sona Koyo Stee	1:1	2006
Harita Seating	1:1	2007
Banco Products	1:1	2007
Bharat Seats	1:1	2007
Bosch Chasis	1:1	2007
JBM Auto Comp	1:2	2007
Motherson Sumi	1:2	2007
Amara Raja Batt	1:2	2008

Source: www.moneycontrol.com

Figure 1
Company Size and Bonus Issues

A specific question to be examined was whether company size was correlated with bonus ratio, in particular whether large companies tended to issue bonus shares in higher ratios as compared to small companies. For this purpose, all bonus issues made during 1991-2009 were broken down according to the size of company (Large, Medium and Small) immediately before each bonus issue. 29 bonus issues were from large scale companies, 16 bonus issues from medium scale companies and only 5 bonus issues from the small scale companies. This shows that the performance of the large scale companies was much better than the medium and small scale companies. There were no bonus issues during 1996-00 by the small scale companies. Figure-1 above also depicts that bonus issues by the large scale companies have declined but that of the medium and small scale companies have increased from 1991-95 to 2000-05. The period 2000-05 was good for medium scale companies with 8 bonus issues (about 37.5 per cent) during the period.

Figure 2
Frequency Distribution of Bonus Issues for Individual Ratios

Figure 2 explains that the bonus ratio 1:1 was most repeatedly used by the 60 per cent companies, 1:2 was used by 24 per cent of the companies and the other ratios were used by 16 per cent of the companies. One trend is noticeable that the bonus ratio of 1:1 was most preferable by the companies.

Figure 3
Five Yearly Trend in Bonus Issues

Figure 3 depicts that the number of bonus issues by the automobile companies had an increasing trend between the period 1991-95, 1996-00 and 2001-05. During the last four years i.e. 2006-09, the number of bonus issue was just 9 (about 18 per cent). One of the reasons behind this may be the global financial crisis during that period.

Figure 4
Annual Trend in Bonus Issues

The annual trend in bonus issues by the automobile industry is analysed in Figure-4. Major fluctuations are noticed during the period 2000-2009. Most of the bonus issues have been made during the year 1995, 1996, 2002, 2004 and 2007. There was no bonus issue in the year 2009. The financial crisis may have been a reason for this.

Conclusions

It is well known fact that a bonus share issue results in a higher outflow of funds in the form of increased dividend payments and reduces the degree of financial flexibility as much as the capitalized resources will no longer available for distribution of dividend in the inadequacy of profits. Therefore, the bonus issues expands the total share holdings, the trading volume and liquidity of the shares, raises the dividend amount, gives substantial tax benefits, and act as a signal of brighter prospects of the company. The issue of bonus share signals a higher growth rate and bright future for the company.

Thus, it can be said that the large scale automobile companies from the public sector were the major participants in the bonus issue during the post liberalization period. This was due to the large scale production and government support to public sectors, which have led to increased reserves in the hands of those large scale companies, thus allowing them for a bonus issue. There was a fall in the frequency of bonus issues during the last four years, i.e., 2006-09. The main reason for this decline was the global financial crises which have ceased the profits of the companies, thus, not allowing them for a bonus issue. The companies were more comfortable with the bonus ratio of 1:1, as the largest proportion of the bonus issues were in this ratio.

References

- Gupta L. C. (1973), *Bonus Shares: A Study of the Dividend and Price Effects of Bonus Share Issues*, Macmillan, India.
- Balachandran B. & Tanner S. (2001), *Bonus Share Issues and Announcement Effect: Australian Evidence*, Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=288743
- Malhotra M., Thenmozhi M., & Arunkumar G. (2007), *Stock Market Reaction and Liquidity Changes Around Bonus Issue Announcement: Evidence from India*. Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=962830
- Satyajit D. & Sweta C. (2008), *Market Reaction Around the Stock Splits and Bonus Issues: Some Indian Evidence*, Retrieved from http://papers.ssrn.com/sol3/papers.cfm?abstract_id=1087200
- Pandey I. M. *Financial Management*, Vikas Publication House Pvt Ltd., India
- BSE Official Directory
- Economic Survey Index
- www.moneycontrol.com
- www.bseindia.com
- www.nseindia.com